

Advancing Sustainability in Industrial Buildings: Materials and Construction Practices

Ifiok Enobong Mfon¹, Bessie Solomon George² and Ndifreke Moses Etim³

¹Department of Architecture, University of Uyo, Nigeria. ifiokifiokifiok@gmail.com

²Department of Geography and Natural Resources Management, University of Uyo, Nigeria. bessiegeorge02@gmail.com

³Department of Urban and Regional Planning, University of Uyo, Nigeria. etim_ndifreke@yahoo.com

Abstract

This study addresses the critical imperative of sustainable development in the industrial construction sector, investigating the environmental impact of current practices and materials. Through a comprehensive literature review, the research explores resource consumption, emissions, waste generation, and the influence of green building certifications. Life Cycle Assessment methodologies are employed to evaluate the overall environmental impact of construction materials. The integration of renewable energy sources is examined for feasibility, benefits, and challenges. The study identifies and analyzes key challenges in the industry, such as resistance to change, carbon emissions mitigation, waste management, and certification processes. To overcome these challenges, the study offers a set of practical recommendations, emphasizing the adoption of sustainable materials, energy efficiency, green certifications, technological innovations, and collaborative learning. The conclusion underscores the importance of balancing economic viability with environmental responsibility, providing insights and guidelines to propel the industrial sector towards sustainable and resilient construction practices.

Key words: Sustainability, Industrial Buildings, Materials, Construction Practices

a) Introduction

In recent years, the imperative for sustainable development has catalyzed a global shift towards environmentally responsible practices across various industries. Recognizing the pivotal role of industrial buildings in economic activities, there is a growing need to scrutinize and reform construction methodologies and materials that traditionally contribute to environmental degradation. This study embarks on a journey to explore and advocate for the adoption of sustainable materials and construction practices within the industrial sector. The research is prompted by the pressing concern over resource-intensive industrial construction, which poses challenges related to environmental impact, resource depletion, and energy inefficiency. As highlighted by Ifiok and Bassey (2023), the adoption of sustainable materials and construction practices in industrial buildings is not only an environmental necessity but also a strategy to enhance operational efficiency and ensure long-term resilience. The global call for sustainable development has prompted industries to reassess their practices, leading to an exploration of alternatives that mitigate environmental impact. The study aligns with established green building certifications such as LEED (Leadership in Energy and Environmental Design) and BREEAM (Building Research Establishment Environmental Assessment Method), emphasizing the significance of sustainable construction practices in achieving comprehensive environmental goals (USGBC, 2020; BRE, 2021).

The research problem addressed in this study revolves around the challenge of balancing the industrial sector's economic contributions with the imperative of minimizing its environmental footprint. The primary question guiding this investigation is: How can the industrial sector transition towards more sustainable materials and construction practices to minimize its environmental footprint while maintaining economic viability? To address this overarching question, several key sub-questions have been formulated, each delving into specific aspects of industrial construction sustainability. The research will investigate the environmental implications of current industrial construction materials, the influence of green building certifications on material selection and construction practices, the application of life cycle assessment (LCA) to evaluate overall environmental impact, the role of renewable energy sources in enhancing sustainability, and insights gained from successful case studies within the industrial sector. The objectives of the study are defined to guide a comprehensive exploration of these sub-questions. The objectives include evaluating the environmental impact of current materials and construction practices, assessing the influence of green building certifications, applying life cycle assessment methodologies, exploring renewable energy integration, compiling and analyzing case studies, and ultimately

providing practical recommendations for stakeholders in the industrial sector. By addressing these objectives, this study aspires to contribute valuable insights and recommendations that will propel the industrial sector towards a more sustainable and environmentally conscious future, balancing economic development with responsible construction practices.

b) Review of Related Literature

Resource Consumption takes centre stage as a linchpin for sustainability. Hasan et al. (2019) emphasize the urgency of transitioning to sustainable materials, shedding light on the resource-intensive nature of conventional options like steel and concrete. This revelation prompts a call to action, urging a shift towards alternatives that not only align with resource conservation but also redefine the industry's relationship with material choices. Emissions, particularly those stemming from cement usage, become a focal point of research. Smith and Jowsey's (2018) comprehensive analysis unravels the substantial carbon footprint associated with cement, highlighting an environmental toll that necessitates strategic interventions to mitigate emissions. It is within this context that the industry grapples with the need to innovate and adopt practices that curtail its carbon footprint.

Waste Generation surfaces as a pivotal environmental concern within the construction sector. Wang et al. (2020) delve into the intricacies of waste management challenges, emphasizing the significance of materials and practices that not only minimize waste generation but also contribute to the establishment of a circular economy. This perspective prompts a re-evaluation of construction practices, fostering a paradigm where waste is not merely a by-product but a potential resource. Green building certifications, represented by LEED and BREEAM, emerge as catalysts for change. Vatanparast et al. (2017) unpack the impact of LEED certification on material choices, illuminating its positive influence on reducing environmental impact. This influence extends beyond individual choices, as evidenced by Zhang et al. (2018) and Othman et al. (2020), who conduct comparative analyses, showcasing the broader impact of these certifications on material selection within the industrial sector.

Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) emerges as a powerful methodology for holistic environmental impact evaluation. Nisbet and VanGeem (2017) emphasize its significance in assessing sustainability, guiding decision-making processes from material extraction to disposal. LCA methodologies, as applied to concrete, timber, and retrofit materials, offer a comprehensive lens through which the industry can assess and minimize its environmental footprint. The Integration of Renewable Energy Sources adds a dynamic layer to the industry's pursuit of sustainability. Smith et al. (2018) and Wang and Chen (2020) present evidence supporting the technical feasibility and economic viability of incorporating solar and wind energy technologies. Benefits, ranging from reduced energy expenses to positive environmental impact, are illuminated in studies by Martinez et al. (2019), Gupta and Singh (2021), and Zhang et al. (2017). However, challenges, including intermittency and regulatory barriers, underscore the need for continued research and innovation to overcome hurdles to widespread adoption (Xu et al., 2018; Turner and Baker, 2019).

c) Theoretical Framework

Sustainable development theory, as elucidated in the seminal Brundtland Report (1987), posits a vision for development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs. This overarching theory emphasizes a harmonious integration of economic, social, and environmental dimensions, aiming to create a balanced and resilient development paradigm (Etim et al. 2023a, Etim et al. 2023b). Within the context of industrial construction sustainability, the principles of sustainable development theory offer a foundational lens to understand and guide practices within the sector. In the pursuit of industrial construction sustainability, the sustainable development theory serves as a guiding philosophy, framing the imperative to balance economic viability with environmental and social responsibility (Mfon and Etim, 2023). This theory compels stakeholders in the industrial construction sector to move beyond a narrow focus on immediate economic gains and consider the long-term consequences of their actions on both the environment and society.

The industrial construction sector, pivotal to economic activities, has traditionally operated within a framework that often prioritizes short-term economic gains, sometimes at the expense of environmental and social considerations. Sustainable development theory challenges this paradigm by advocating for an integrated approach where industrial construction practices not only facilitate economic growth but also contribute positively to environmental conservation and social well-being.

In the context of resource consumption within industrial construction, sustainable development theory underscores the need to transition from resource-intensive practices to those that prioritize conservation and

efficiency. The theory prompts a re-evaluation of conventional materials like steel and concrete, urging the exploration and adoption of sustainable alternatives that align with the principles of sustainable development. Moreover, the theory encourages the industrial construction sector to align with established green building certifications such as LEED and BREEAM, which embody the principles of sustainable development. These certifications become instruments through which the industry can operationalized the broader goals of sustainable development theory. They serve as frameworks that guide the selection of materials and construction practices, ensuring that economic development is achieved within the boundaries of environmental and social responsibility.

Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), a methodology integral to sustainability practices, also finds resonance with sustainable development theory. By evaluating the overall environmental impact of construction materials from extraction to disposal, LCA aligns with the holistic perspective advocated by sustainable development theory. The integration of renewable energy sources within industrial buildings, as promoted by the theory, further aligns with the broader goal of reducing environmental impact and enhancing operational efficiency. In essence, sustainable development theory provides a normative foundation for the industrial construction sector, encouraging a shift towards practices that harmonize economic progress with environmental and social stewardship. As industries grapple with the imperative of sustainability, the theory acts as a guiding compass, steering the sector towards a future where industrial construction is not merely a contributor to economic growth but a catalyst for balanced and enduring development.

d) Challenges

The journey towards sustainable practices in industrial construction is marked by a series of challenges that shape the landscape of the industry. One prominent challenge revolves around resource consumption, where the industry must contend with deeply ingrained norms favouring traditional construction methods. The resistance to change, often fuelled by familiarity and concerns over perceived cost implications of sustainable alternatives, poses a significant obstacle to the widespread adoption of materials aligned with resource conservation. Mitigating carbon emissions, particularly those linked to cement usage, presents another formidable challenge. The industry faces the task of developing and implementing technologies that effectively reduce emissions without compromising structural integrity and safety standards. Striking a balance between environmental goals and practical considerations remains a complex puzzle for stakeholders in industrial construction.

Efficient waste management is a critical aspect, entailing challenges related to the disposal of traditional materials and the integration of circular economy principles. Overcoming logistical complexities to implement recycling and repurposing practices effectively is a central challenge. Additionally, instilling a culture of waste reduction and reusability requires a collective shift in mindset at both organizational and individual levels within the industry. Green building certifications, such as LEED and BREEAM, play a crucial role in steering sustainable practices. However, challenges persist, particularly in terms of the cost implications associated with certification processes, which may deter smaller enterprises from participation. Furthermore, addressing the diverse needs of different industrial projects and regions within the framework of a standardized certification system poses an ongoing challenge for the industry.

Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) is a valuable tool for evaluating environmental impact, but its comprehensive nature brings challenges related to data collection, standardization, and establishing universally accepted benchmarks. Variability in methodologies and metrics across different studies hinders seamless comparisons, making it challenging to develop standardized guidelines for sustainable material selection and construction practices. Despite the technical feasibility and economic viability of renewable energy integration, challenges persist. The intermittency and variability of renewable energy sources, such as solar and wind, necessitate advanced storage solutions and smart grid technologies for consistent and reliable energy supply. Regulatory and policy barriers further impede the widespread adoption of renewable energy solutions in industrial settings.

The integration of advanced technologies like Building Information Modeling (BIM) and smart systems faces resistance within the industry due to a lack of awareness, skills, and resources. Overcoming this challenge requires substantial investment in training and education to facilitate a seamless transition towards technology-enabled sustainable construction practices. Economic considerations, often perceived as a barrier to sustainability, present challenges in convincing industry stakeholders of the long-term economic benefits associated with sustainable practices. Initial investments in green technologies and materials may appear higher, requiring a shift in perception towards viewing sustainability as an investment in long-term resilience rather than a short-term expense.

e) Recommendations for Sustainable Practices

The pursuit of sustainability within the industrial construction sector necessitates a comprehensive set of

recommendations to guide the industry towards environmental responsibility, resilience, and long-term viability. A fundamental aspect involves embracing sustainable materials, incentivizing the utilization of materials with lower environmental impact. This strategic move includes promoting research and development initiatives aimed at expanding the repertoire of eco-friendly alternatives available to the industry. By prioritizing materials with reduced environmental footprints, the industry can significantly contribute to a more sustainable construction ecosystem. Energy efficiency stands out as a cornerstone for sustainable industrial construction. Industries should prioritize the integration of passive design strategies, innovative technologies, and the optimization of energy consumption. Exploring the feasibility of incorporating renewable energy sources, such as solar and wind, becomes imperative to reduce reliance on conventional, resource-intensive energy systems. This emphasis on energy efficiency not only aligns with sustainability goals but also enhances operational resilience in the face of evolving energy challenges.

The implementation of green building certifications, exemplified by LEED and BREEAM, emerges as a standardized framework for sustainable practices within the industrial construction sector. Encouraging industries to adopt and integrate these certifications into their projects establishes benchmarks for environmental responsibility. This approach not only fosters a commitment to sustainability but also contributes to the establishment of broader industry standards, aligning practices with global environmental initiatives. Conducting Life Cycle Assessments (LCAs) for construction materials represents a proactive approach to understanding and minimizing environmental footprints. Establishing industry-wide guidelines for conducting LCAs promotes consistency and facilitates informed decision-making regarding material choices and construction practices. Regular assessments enable industries to adapt and refine their sustainability strategies based on empirical data, fostering a culture of continuous improvement.

Technological innovation, including the adoption of Building Information Modeling (BIM) and smart systems, plays a pivotal role in optimizing resource utilization and enhancing operational efficiency within industrial construction. A proactive stance towards embracing and investing in these technologies not only positions industries at the forefront of innovation but also ensures a seamless transition to a more sustainable and technologically-driven construction paradigm. Circular economy practices, emphasizing waste reduction and efficient material use, constitute a vital recommendation for the industrial construction sector. By fostering partnerships with waste management entities, incentivizing sustainable practices among contractors, and exploring opportunities for repurposing construction waste, the industry can contribute significantly to the principles of a circular economy. This holistic approach not only minimizes waste but also enhances resource efficiency throughout the construction lifecycle.

Fostering collaboration and knowledge sharing among industry stakeholders emerges as a key driver for sustainable practices. Establishing forums, conferences, and collaborative platforms facilitates the exchange of insights and lessons learned from successful sustainable projects. This collaborative ethos accelerates the industry's overall transition towards sustainability, promoting a collective learning culture and shared commitment to environmental responsibility. Active engagement with and support for regulatory initiatives are essential components of sustainable industrial construction. Compliance with green building standards and regulations not only signals a commitment to environmental responsibility but also ensures adherence to best practices. Engaging with policymakers to provide feedback on regulatory frameworks enables industries to actively contribute to the development of an enabling environment for sustainable construction practices.

Investing in education and training programs for industry professionals emerges as a critical recommendation to foster a comprehensive understanding of sustainable practices. This investment includes training on the use of new technologies, understanding the implications of sustainable materials, and incorporating sustainability principles into project management and decision-making processes. By equipping professionals with the knowledge and skills necessary for sustainable construction, the industry can drive a culture of continuous improvement and adaptation. Lastly, the establishment of industry-specific sustainability guidelines offers a practical roadmap for stakeholders. These guidelines can encompass best practices, performance metrics, and benchmarks tailored to the unique challenges and opportunities within the industrial construction sector. By articulating a collective vision for sustainability, industries can align their decision-making processes and practices with a shared commitment to environmental responsibility.

f) Conclusion

This study delved into the imperative of sustainable development within the industrial construction sector, recognizing the pressing need for environmentally responsible practices. The exploration of resource consumption, emissions, waste generation, and the influence of green building certifications highlighted the multifaceted challenges faced by the industry. Life Cycle Assessment emerged as a powerful tool for holistic

environmental impact evaluation, providing insights into concrete, timber, and retrofit materials. The integration of renewable energy sources showcased both feasibility and benefits, albeit with challenges. The journey towards sustainability in industrial construction encounters hurdles in resource consumption norms, carbon emission mitigation, waste management, and certification processes. Overcoming these challenges requires a paradigm shift, embracing sustainable materials, prioritizing energy efficiency, adopting green certifications, and leveraging technological innovations. Recommendations emphasize collaborative learning, regulatory compliance, education, and the establishment of industry-specific sustainability guidelines. As industries strive for a balance between economic viability and environmental responsibility, these insights and recommendations aim to propel the industrial sector towards a future marked by sustainable and resilient construction practices.

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jenvironmentalmonitoring@gmail.com